

BENEFITS OF INTERACTIVE MUSIC THERAPY ON CHILDREN WITH AUTISM

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ABSTRACT

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder with a wide range of severity, encompassing mild to severe levels of social, communicative, cognitive, and behavioral functioning. This social functioning disorder affects every 1 in 68 children born in the U.S., with prevalence rates doubling since 2000. ASD is associated with left hemisphere responsibilities, such as decreased joint attention, inability to comprehend social cues, insufficient linguistic knowledge, and a difficulty forming meaningful relationships. Children with ASD are faced with many problems, including a lack of friends, limited social activities, and are often excluded from mainstream school. Unfortunately, they are also frequently kept from valuable social, educational, and leisurely life experiences; from not being able to pick out their own clothes, to learning how to drive or becoming independent, the daily struggles of autism hinder them from living “normal” lives. In the most severe cases, some will commit crimes during adolescence due to their frustration and inability to control their aggression or understand other's perspectives. The symptoms of autism impact not only familial relationships, but a family's financial stability as well. Parents of autistic children often feel isolated, depressed, and emotionally and physically exhausted from the strenuous care involved in caring for and supporting their children. In a study of 196,159 households conducted by Saunders et. al. (2015), 52% of caregivers and parents of autistic children reported having financial difficulty, with many having to leave work to care for their children. However, these problems can be alleviated by providing an effective and appropriate therapy regimen that will not only help autistic children live more “normal” lives, but allow them to better integrate as active members of society, benefiting themselves and those who care around them.

Keywords: Autism spectrum disorder, psychological process

INTRODUCTION

Traditional social skill and communication therapies such as Pivotal Response Treatment (PRT) and Applied Behavioral Analysis (ABA) have helped many families and children diagnosed with ASD. However, they are concealing the benefits of using a more creative and flexible form of therapy more often: music therapy. Where speech therapies such as ABA and PRT are more structured and focused around specific

objectives, music offers a means of self-expression, communication and interaction that can be more easily assimilated by children with autism. From previous studies, it is clear that music therapy provides an additional aspect to just the traditional patient-therapist treatment. Specifically, Wigram (2006), a professor of Music therapy in Aalong University, states that “music therapy has been recommended as an effective treatment in facilitating communication, as music is a medium that involves a complex range of expressive qualities, dynamic form and dialogue, and offers a means by which some form of alternative communication can be established to help achieve engagement, interaction and successful relationships” .

More importantly, interactive and improvisational music therapy can circumvent monotonous and inefficient practices in learning social communication and behavioral skills that traditional therapies such as ABA and PRT often use. Unlike the creative format of music therapy, speech and occupational therapies rely on structured therapy sessions to achieve specific goals, obstructing the child’s naturally artistic thinking. So, can interactive music therapy really be an effective tool to overcome developmental obstacles in children with ASD? An increase in education and use of interactive music therapy can revolutionize current therapy protocol and allow for more efficient improvements in emotional expression, social responsiveness, and behavioral aspects that affect over 1% of the entire world population. In addition, the faster rate of improvement, greater number of verbal attempts, as well as the significant improvement in number of words said in the home environment might have been contributed to an increased motivation of the child to complete the task when melody and rhythm were implemented. So, if individuals with autism demonstrate strengths in tasks associated with the right cerebral hemisphere, such as creativity and imagination, then it may be expected that individuals with autism might show an affinity for tasks relating to music and rhythm. Sandiford, Mainess, and Daher continue to explain that, “research indicates an increase in fibers in the corpus callosum in those exposed to music, potentially allowing for better transfer of information,” thus explaining how the corpus callosum, an area of impairment in children with autism, can be greatly helped with MBCT. This example utilizes scientific and behavioral analysis of 12 autistic children to show the many potential uses of music therapy. The anatomical aspect of evaluating the effect of music therapy bolsters the argument that music therapy is an effective way to help children appropriately communicate and better assimilate into society.

Although it is clear that music therapy is exceedingly valuable to an autistic child’s early age development, many autistic children still do not receive music therapy treatment, often due to accessibility and financial reasons. As an autistic child enters school age curriculum, an individualized education plan (IEP) is written to ensure the

child receives appropriate services while in school. An IEP is a legal document created by parents and an IEP committee of therapists and school administrators that explicitly describes the child's needs, the services the school will provide, and how progress will be measured. This process is extremely cumbersome, as only after an IEP meeting is held, an evaluation is requested, an evaluation is conducted, and an IEP meeting is held to discuss results, is the autistic child approved for therapy. Unlike occupational, speech, or other more "convenient" traditional therapies, music therapy is considered a "related service," which is a list of services biasedly deemed unnecessary by the school IEP committee. So, when school districts interpret a related service list as exhaustive, many services cannot, and will not be legally provided. In many cases, interactive music therapy is kept off this list due to financial and accessibility reasons. School administrators, often illegally, predetermine that they do not offer the service, because if the IEP team concludes the child requires the service, then it must be provided. For example, if a school district is held responsible for providing music therapy to autistic children, but no local board-certified music therapist is available, then the district will have to pay for the relocation and salary of the music therapist, often an avoidable expenditure. Due to these many reasons, some school districts do not provide the financially inopportune music therapy service. If a child will greatly benefit from the advantages of music therapy, it is unjust to refuse an essential service.

CONCLUSION

Although there is still more research to be done, many studies demonstrate how effective and motivating music can be to help children function across many domains. As more quantitative research is conducted in the field of music therapy for children with autism, this therapy may soon be recognized as an established treatment rather than an emerging one. The modern world has progressed towards interdisciplinarity in many realms of society, which can be directly applied to services such as music therapy. Therefore, it is imperative to further investigate this as a non traditional outlet for autism treatment, and not allow it to be overlooked as it has been in the past.

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